

www.arseam.com
Impact Factor: 0.98

THE CHANGING CONTOURS OF INDIAN BANKING : INTERNATIONAL BENCHMARKING AND AGENDA OF REFORMS

Ganga Kumar

M.D.

Bihar State Building Construction Corporation Ltd., Government of Bihar,
Vishweshsaraia Bhawan, Patna, Bihar, India

ABSTRACT

The world is in the midst of several financial crisis. Over the past 20 years major financial disruptions have taken place roughly every three years, starting with the savings and loans collapse and credit crunch of the late 1980s and the early 1990s down to the unfolding developments in the global financial markets following the US subprime mortgage crisis in August 2007 and deepened as stock markets worldwide crashed in September 2008. Indian financial sector and the banking industry would not have escape in face of any global financial crisis because our economy has become more integrated with the rest of world financial markets.. In fact, India is going forward of its agenda for second generation financial sector reforms which goes much beyond the adherence to the ensuring international standards and into meeting the requirements of a high growth economy as well as providing development, both in the short term and over the medium term.

In this given perspective of the changing landscape of banking industry in India's financial system, an attempt has been made in this paper to overview the growth and structure of Indian banking system in India's economic development particularly after financial sector liberalisation that has led to transformation of Indian banking sector over the past two decades with the observations to find out the relevant answers to the strength, weakness, opportunities and the threat to Indian banking sector in the midst of dislocation in global market both in the present and in future.

Key words: *Benchmarking, liberalisation, Indian banking sector,*

INTRODUCTION:

The world is in the midst of several financial crisis.¹ Over the past 20 years major financial disruptions have taken place roughly every three years, starting with the savings and loans collapse and credit crunch of the late 1980s and the early 1990s down to the unfolding developments in the global financial markets following the US subprime mortgage crisis in August 2007 and deepened as stock markets worldwide crashed in September 2008.(Table 1).² Indian financial sector and the banking industry would not have escape in face of any global financial crisis because our economy has become more integrated with the rest of world financial markets. Moreover, over the past two decades, overseas finance has become increasingly important for Indian financial sector in general and banking industry in particular from the angle of higher liquidity conditions with a constant fiscal and monetary stimulus for financial stability and growing liquidity of the banking sector as the prime policy

objective to the overall growth of Indian the economy³. Furthermore, during the post the crisis of 2007-09, financial stability is regarded as a prime policy to Indian banking system in the light of sovereign debt problems in advance economy which has indeed; reaffirmed the importance of pursuing financial sector reforms with banking sector financial soundness. In fact, India is going forward of its agenda for second generation financial sector reforms which goes much beyond the adherence to the ensuring international standards and into meeting the requirements of a high growth economy as well as providing development, both in the short term and over the medium term.⁴

Apart from these issues, the greater role of banking sector in India rests on the RBI policy perspectives to focus on bank linkage model and financial inclusion and inclusive growth to make financial services assessable to all in general with urban or rural population but more as to those excluded section of the society facing problems in undertaking even simple transactions. The present government with the initiative undertaken by Prime Minister Modi has now given, implemented and executed “Jan-Dhan Yojana” making financial equality of the majority of poor by opening up their saving bank account in different banks even at zero balance. Thus, the key drive of India’s vision of inclusive growth put forward in 11th and 12th Five Year Plan Highlighting financial inclusion that seems to be broadcasted and making it practical by the present BJP government at center. The vision and initiative, RBI need a strategic support from the banks as a social responsibility and not compulsion to achieve the millennium development goal achievement for bringing about more excluded people to the banking fold and evolve a road map for accessing financial services and timely and adequate credit needed by the vulnerable groups at an affordable cost.⁵ Notwithstanding the multitude of challenges, the regulatory responses and the inherent strengths underlying, the Indian economy should ensure that the banking system continues to play a positive role in supporting the financial needs of our growing economy.

The ongoing structural changes that have grown in a specific kind of environment both national and international scenario with a strong bearing on the operation and management of a very comprehensive structure of India’s financial system constituting variety of banks, financial institutions and capital market. particularly with respect to branch network, market share, employment, deposit mobilisation, credit deployment, income and expenditure composition in the midst of a several financial crisis arising out of three channels. viz ; trade channel, the financial channel and making of high degree of inflationary pressures and thereby losing of the confidence channel. In the light of the existing conditions and the

emerging issues, the paper finds out the relevant answers to the strength, weakness, opportunities and the threat to Indian banking sector in the midst of dislocation in global market both in the present as well as in future.

The Major Features of Indian Financial System and the Growth and Structure of Banking Sector : An Overview

Modern banking in India could be traced back to the establishment of Bank of Bengal (January 2, 1809), the first joint stock bank sponsored by Government of Bengal and governed by the Royal Charter of the British India Government. It was followed by establishment of Bank of Bombay (April 15, 1840) and Bank of Madras (July 1, 1843). These three banks, known as the presidency banks, marked the beginning for the limited liability and joint stock banking in India and were also invested with the right of note issue. In the banking field, after nationalisation there has been an unprecedented growth and diversification of banking industry with has been so stupendous that it has no parallel in the annals of banking anywhere in the world. During the last 45 years i.e. from 1969, tremendous changes have taken place in the banking industry. The banks have not only shed their traditional functions and but also have been innovating, improving and coming out with new PPP model in bank services such as e-banking and mobile banking et. in both rural and urban areas to cater to the emerging needs of their customers.

However, establishment of banking of the western type was attempted only as late as 1683 by the East India Company. Today Indian banking has come a long way since then in terms of complexity of operations and the elaborateness of the structure. Moreover, Indian banking system has come to acquire certain peculiarities of its own not found in the banking system in the other countries.

The policy of financial sector reforms as a signal of banking reforms as well as a part of the new economic policy in India has had run more than 25 years by now. The key words which express the major planks of these policies are privatization, marketization, liberalization, deregulation, competition and globalization. Following the launching of reforms, the Indian financial markets have undergone many significant changes and many more changes are looming large on the financial horizon. The current policy has quickened the pace of structural transformation of the Indian Financial System (IFS), and has laid the basis for the

emergence of a changing structure of certain character in Indian Banking Industry . However, all is not well with the IFS; there is a dark side to its development. The “state of credit” or the “State of confidence” happens to be quite low in our financial sector.

Financial restructuring essentially, therefore; involves a normative proach, a vision how the financial system may be made viable, stable, sustainable, safe, sound, economically and socially efficient so as to make the growth and structure of Indian banking system as people oriented attainment of financial inclusion and inclusive growth.

The Salient Features of the Indian Financial System:

As historical and evolutionary knowledge enables one to develop a correct and proper perspective on current policies and future development, we present below a brief retrospect of the structural and other features of the IFS on the eve of financial reforms (see Bhole,1992).⁶

(1) The IFS has grown enormously since 1950 in terms of size, innovations diversity, complexity, and sophistication. All the indicators of financial development, namely the Finance Ratio, Financial Interrelation Ratio, New Issue Ratio and Intermediation Ratio have increased significantly. A considerable widening, deepening and geographical spread of the financial institutions and markets have taken place over the period of time. The access to finance, financial services, financial instruments etc. by an increasing number of people in all areas including rural areas has been achieved.

(2) The IFS has amply fulfilled the function of promotion of saving and investment. The rates of saving and investment have increased from about 10 per cent to about 24 per cent during 1951-1995. However, the growth in this respect appears to have reached a plateau over the past 10-25 years.

(3) Unlike in many other countries, in India, the household sector accounts for the major part (75 to 80 per cent) of aggregate savings. The contribution of the public sector and private corporate sector in this respect has been rather small.

(4) There has been a substantial increase in the financialization and institutionalization of savings in India. Disintermediation and securitization cannot be said to have taken place significantly so far.

(5) The most preferred assets of the investors even now is bank and other deposits, and other debt instruments. In spite of the attention it has received in the media, the “equity culture” has not developed much.

(6) Although the banking system remains the largest part of the IFS even now, other financial institutions also have grown over a period of time, and now they account for 50 to 55 per cent of the size of operations of the banking system in terms of outstanding credit or the annual increase in outstanding credit or the aggregate financial assets.

(7) The secondary markets in different financial instruments have remained underdeveloped so far. The markets for many financial instruments are narrow, and the institutional ownership of even the corporate securities has increased over the period of time.

(8) Almost all the interest rates have been administered by the authorities for a long period of time.

(9) The financial markets in India are marketed by centralization, concentration and oligopolistic or monopolistic imperfections. They are almost entirely owned and closely controlled, regulated and monitored by the Government.

(10) Financial development has often taken place in spurts and as a result of fiscal concessions. The investors often feel cheated in respect of risk, return and liquidity of financial assets. Banks and financial institutions have suffered from an increase in non performing assets, bad debts, low profitability and sickness. The enormous financial development has failed to produce creditable economic development in terms of quantity and quality.

The major objectives of financial sector reforms are said to be as follows:-⁷

- a) To promote a diversified, viable, efficient, transparent and competitive financial system,
- b) To increase a locative efficiency of available savings.
- c) To increase return on investment
- d) To promote competition by creating a level playing field and allowing free entry and exit particularly to private sector institutions.
- e) To ensure that flexible and market interest rates, along with some concessional rates prevail in the markets
- f) To modernize the instruments of monetary control so as to make them more suitable for the conduct of monetary policy in a market economy, i.e. to replace physical controls on monetary variables by instruments based on market incentives.
- g) To promote accelerated growth of the real sector. Specifically, reforms are directed to improve the financial health and conditions of banks, and to develop stock markets and equity culture in the country.

On the whole, the post crisis regulatory and supervisory developments in India are based not on the lessons from the past, but are being guided more by future needs of the economy by exploring ways to liberalize the licensing of new banks, presence of foreign banks, bank holding company structure for the financial conglomerates and above all, the financial inclusion of the excluded majority of population in the financial landscape of banking for their inclusive empowerment.⁸

Structure and the Pattern of Ownership of Commercial Banks in India

There has been unprecedented expansion of banking operations in India.⁹ There were 298 banks in 2002-03 but due to the process of amalgamation, mergers and consolidation of banks, the number of banks declined drastically. clearly show that total number of commercial banks declined to 167 in the year 2012-13. At present there are 4 non scheduled banks in India. The total number of bank branches increased from 53286 in the years 1986-87 to 76696 in 2012-13. The impact of this phenomenal growth was to bring down the population per branch from 6000 in the year 1986-87 to 14000 in 2012-13.¹⁰

At present, the Indian banking system consists of 26 public sector banks, 20 private sector banks, 43 foreign banks, 56 regional rural banks, 1,589 urban cooperative banks and 93,550 rural cooperative banks, in addition to cooperative credit institutions. The Indian banking sector's assets reached US\$ 1.8 trillion in FY14 from US\$ 1.3 trillion in FY10, with 70 per cent of it being accounted by the public sector.

Total lending and deposits increased at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 20.7 per cent and 19.7 per cent, respectively, during FY07-14 and are further poised for growth, backed by demand for housing and personal finance. Total asset size of banking sector assets is expected to increase to US\$ 28.5 trillion by FY25. Deposite have grows at a CAGR of 13.6 per cent during FY05-15 to an estimated US\$1.48 trillion in FY15. Deposit growth has been mainly driven by strong growth in saving amid rising disposable income levels.

Moreover, Indian banks are increasingly focusing on adopting integrated approach to risk management. Banks have already embraced the international banking supervision accord of Basel IKI. According to RBI, majority of the banks already meet capital requirements of Basel III, which has a deadline of March 31, 2019. Most of the banks have put in place the framework for asset-liability match, credit and derivatives risk management.

Apart from these developments, one of the important aspects is the rising incomes of the poor section are expected to enhance the need for banking services in rural areas and

therefore drive the growth of the sector, programmes like MNREGA have helped in increasing rural income aided by the recent Jan Dhan Yojana. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) has relaxed its branch licensing policy, thereby allowing banks (which meet certain financial parameters) to set-up new branches in tier-2 to tier-6 centers, without prior approval from RBI. It has emphasized the need to focus on spreading the reach of banking services to the un-banked population of India.

The steady deposit growth and healthy credit growth over the period i.e from 2005 to 2015 which make it clear the following trends:

- Deposits have grown at a CAGR of 13.6 per cent during FY05-14 and reached US\$ 1.5 trillion.
- Deposit growth has been mainly driven by strong growth in savings amid rising disposable income levels.
- Access to the banking system has also improved over the years due to persistent government efforts to promote banking technology, and promote expansion in unbanked and non-metropolitan regions.
- Credit off-take has been surging ahead over the past decade, aided by strong economic growth, rising disposable incomes, increasing consumerism and easier access to credit.
- Total credit extended went up to us\$ 1,089 billion by FY15
- Credit to non-food industries increased 9.75 per cent to us\$ 1,073.4 billion in FY15, from the previous financial year
- Demand has grown for both corporate and retail loans.

Different States of the Development of Indian Banking System

- Establishment of the RBI in 1935 through RBI Act, 1934.
- Nationalization of RBI in January 1st, 1949.
- With a view to have the coordinated regulation of Indian banking, the banking regulation act was passed in March 1949.
- Imperial bank of India was partially nationalized in 1st July 1955 and it was named as the State Bank of India” Along with it other 8 (at present 7) banks were converted as its associated bank which form what is named as the state bank group.

- IDBI established under industrial development bank of India act, 1964 for providing credit and other facilities for developing industries. Of course later it has been converge into as a banking company.
- 14 large commercial banks whose reserves were more than Rs.50 crore each were nationalized on 19th July,1969.
- 1971; Creation of credit guarantee corporation.
- RRB' came into existence on 2nd October,1975 and are being governed by RRB Act 1976.
- After one decade of first nationalization of 14 banks, on April 15th, 1980, those 6 private sector banks.
- whose revenues were more than Rs.200 crores each were nationalized.
- EXIM bank was established in January 1st, 1982 for financing, facilitating and promoting foreign trade in India.
- Establishment of NABARD in July 12th, 1982.
- SIDBI was established in 1989 under Small Industries Development Bank of India Act, 1989.
- Setting up of CGTMSE (Credit Guarantee Fund Trust for Medium and Small Enterprises) in August 2000 to provide guarantee support to banks and lending institutions for their exposure to the MSE sector. This is the only credit guarantee institution in the country exclusively set up for the benefit of entrepreneurs in the MSE sector.

1. Structural Changes in Market Share

In the banking industry, the market share is best represented by the volume of business done by a bank. The components of business in the Indian banking industry as showing indicate the fact that 52.19 per cent of the total business is in the hands of nationalized banks. Next 23.28 percent is with business is with the public sector banks. The share of private banks is 18.56 per cent and that of foreign bank is 5.97 per cent. The breakup of total business into its components is exactly in consonance with total business. Thus public sector banks still form a major chunk of business in the Indian banking industry.¹¹

2. Structure of Market Reach and Employment

In addition to market share, the reach of the service firm also determines its performance. The reach depends upon the number of branches and manpower the firm has in the market. The bank group wise distribution of total number of branches and employment in the Indian banking in the year 2013-14 shows that the share of nationalized banks in the total number of branches is on the tune of 60.14 percent and the share of SBI and its associate's bank group is 24.92 percent. In all 85.06 percent of the total branches are with the public sector banks. The share of private banks and foreign banks in terms of branches is 14.5 percent and 0.44 percent respectively. It shows that foreign banks are less than one-half percent in terms of number of branches. Similarly in terms of manpower, table indicates that 77.77 per cent of the total employment of banking industry is with public sector banks. Private banks have share of just 19.30 percent and foreign banks have 2.93 percent of the total employment. Overall banking industry average employment per branch comes out to be 14. As compared to this benchmark irrespective of branch size, public sector banks have a staff of just 12 per branch, as against 18 per branch in private banks and the market of 90 per branch in foreign banks.¹²

3. Group-wise Income and Expenditure of Commercial Banks

The income of commercial banks is derived from the services rendered it. The main sources of operation revenue of commercial banks are interest and discount on loans, dividend on investments, services charges on deposit accounts, other services charges and fee. Commercial banks total expenditure is composed of interest expenditure paid on deposits and borrowings and other expenditure which includes operating expenditure (establishment expenditure) and provisions and contingencies. Interest on deposits comprises a major component of interest expenditure. Operating expenditure which is represented by wage bill, rent, taxes, printing, stationery, advertisement, publicity, director's fees, allowances, postage, telegrams, insurance, repair and maintenance constitutes other important expenses. The major items on provisions and contingencies consist of provisions for losses, provisions for depreciation in value of investments and provisions for taxes.¹³

The total income and expenditure of banking industry in India Makes It evident that in terms of total income, the share of nationalized banks in the total industry in the year 2013-14 is 49.9 percent. The share of SBI and its associates turns out to be 22.59 per cent. In all 72.51 percent income is with public sector banks. The share of Indian private banks is 20.58 percent whereas share of foreign banks is just 6.91 percent. The behavior of total expenditure is

exactly in tune with the behavior of total income. So scale-wise also the major share is formed by the Indian public sector banks.¹⁴

4. Role of Commercial Banks for Financial Inclusion and inclusive Growth:

Financial inclusion is intended to connect people with banks. Banks play an important role in inclusive growth. Banks are the key pillars of India's financial system. Commercial banks are now slowly coming to appreciate the business potential in financial inclusion and also the need for better involvement. Commercial Banks providing basic banking services to the rural people through these low cost devices, without the concomitant costs associated with setting up of an extension Counter /ATM or a Branch and thus aiming to bring down significantly the transaction costs in rural banking. The Bank developed the operating model to cover a large number of unbanked villages.¹⁵

A broad financial strategy for financial inclusion in India in relation to banking system has been developed. It covers uses highly sophisticated technology, emphasis financial literacy and credit counseling, advising banks to open zero balance account etc. Even though number of strategies are developed, it is no free from challenges. Major challenges are:

- (i) From the perspective of the banks, providing such services would have various risk associated with it. The major risks to the banks are legal reputation and operational risks. These risks are to be managed with tight and regular monitoring, developing systems and procedures and by developing effective risk management tools and matrix.
- (ii) The banks are faced with high operating cost in extending the financial services to the remote areas. High maintenance cost of these accounts as well as small ticket size of the transactions is also adding to the problem.
- (iii) People may not have adequate knowledge in bank dealings. Financial Literacy programmes need to be implemented.
- (iv) Even though the number of branches established in under developed, the commercial banks could not be able to mobilize maximum targeted deposit because of the scattered population and poor savings habit of residents. The Bank observed that man of the villages were reluctant to visit the bank branches for various reasons like long distance to be travelled time lost, difficulty in following procedures and reluctance to visit branches for small value transactions.

- (v). Poor recovery of loans and advances increases the amount of Non Performing Asset (NPA) effective policy implementation is required in this area.

Conclusion

Out of the entire analytical, discussion it appears that the Indian financial system has changed considerably over the past twenty four years consequently interest rates have been deregulated and competition and efficiency in banking business has increased and well developed with different classes of banks - public sector banks, foreign banks, private banks in general and regional rural banks and cooperative banks in particular. They have achieved tremendous progress over the years in terms of various parameters such as growth of branches, modified deposits of assets creation, credit, deployment, market share, income and expenditure composition vis-à-vis a broad financial services for financial inclusion for inclusive growth at an affordable cost to the vast sections of the disadvantaged and low income groups.

Thus the Indian Financial system has changed considerably after post liberalization. Interest rates have been regulated and competition and efficiency in the banking business has increased with new entrants being allowed. Since 2009, the financial sector reforms in India transform a new impetus with India joining hands with the international community in the past crisis reform of financial regulation, and playing a key role in the ongoing initiative through international forces like the G20, the IMF and the BIS in designing new regulatory and supervisory structure.¹⁶

The progress of the reforms in India in the post crisis period has been remarkable considering a spate of measures being taken to improve financial soundness of banking sector which is a sine qua non for the financial stability in a bank dominated country. In terms of financial soundness indicators, the Indian banking system compares favorably to those of the other G 20 countries.¹⁷ The major indicators of the Indian banking system in the period following the crisis have not shown an adverse developments and the performance of Indian banks remained robust 2010-11. A series of stress tests conducted by the Reserve Bank in respect of credit, liquidity and interest rate risks shown the banks are reasonably resilient. By streamlining the financial sector laws, rules and regulation and bring them in harmony with the requirement of a modern innovative banking sector, India is, therefore ;exploring as well as working more on liberalizing the licensing of new banks, presence of foreign banks, bank holding company structure for financial conglomerates. An effective transformation in these areas have of course the potential of changing the financial landscape and thereby giving a

constant fresh oxygen to a new imperative for growth and structure of Indian banking system.¹⁹ The skilled banking operational system is the only answer to the efficient activating innovative banking structure to Indian banking industry.

Figure-1

THE STRUCTURE OF INDIAN BANKING SECTOR

Source: RBI

Table-1

Major Global Financial Crises since the 1990

Nature of crises	Reasons
ERM crisis of 1992-93 Affected the countries under the Exchange Rate Mechanism	The ERM crisis brought into focus the stability of speculators to precipitate a crisis and the limited ability of available foreign exchange reserves to stem the run on a currency in a world of volatile capital flows. The ERM crisis also highlighted the trade off between monetary and exchange rate management policies under a convertible currency.
Currency crisis in Mexico in 1994-95 which graduated into a debt crisis	Volatile capital flows resulted in a currency crisis, which graduated into a debt crisis with the inability of the government to redeem the 'lesebonos', which were short term debt instrument repayable in Pesos but were indexed to the US dollar issues by the Mexican Government.
East Asian currency crisis which started that were with the collapse of the Thai Baht in July 1997 engulfed other Asian countries like South Korea, Indonesia, Phillippines and Malaysia	The crisis reflected a typical case of structural imbalance and some major deficiencies in the affected economies. Uncontrolled capital account liberalization the back of weak financial systems characterized by or monitoring and surveillance inappropriate policy stances such as pegged exchange rates and unlimited access to foreign currency loans for the private sector led to the crisis. Lack of timely and adequate financial assistance from the multilateral institutions, at least initially seems to have exacerbated the crisis.
Russian currency crisis in August 1998	Faced with significantly large capital outflows in he face of inadequate reserves, Russia defaulted on its domestic and external debt in August 1998. It subsequently devalued its currency, thereby disrupting the international economy to a certain extent.
Brazilian currency crisis in February 1999	In February 1999, following months of speculative pressure and in spite of a large IMF rescue package, the Brazilian Real was devalued, Reasons included volatile capital flows and fundamental problems associated with the

Ganga Kumar/ The Changing Contours of Indian Banking : International Benchmarking And Agenda of Reforms

	adoption of the Real Plan (1994) to control hyperinflation. Inadequate fiscal consolidation also led to fear of default high interest rates, and a consequent debt spiral.
Argentinean crisis in September 2001	In September 2001, Argentina defaulted on almost US \$ 3 billion debt owed by it to the IMF. Interactions between an un stainable fiscal regime and the existing currency board arrangement in the face of unfavorable external developments were the most crucial elements in the Argentine crisis
Crisis in Turkey in 2001	The immediate cause of crisis in Tukey in 2001 was a combination of portfolio losses and liquidity problems in a few banks, which triggered a loss of confidence in the entire banking system leading to a reversal of capital flows. The Turkis Lira was devalued by 30 per cent in February 2001 and the Government adopted a floating exchange rate regime to keep most of its reserves intact.
US Sub prime crisis And Liquidity in July 2007. In Sept 2008, the crisis depended worldwide in stock market	The crisis created concern on TES. They included Economy, Energy, Exchange Rates, and Crunch external Imbalances, Europe/Ero/ ECB, Emerging market economy East as in Middle East, East Asia Far East and Earning/quit markets. The US Economy had four cascading impact viz. a) sharp decline in consumer's spending a houses b) Huge default on mortgage payments c) capital loss for bad mortgage and bankruptcy of banks forced merger with stronger banks and d) Lack of crashed confidence in interbank transactions.

NOTES AND REFERENCES

1. For a comprehensive study see Bergsten, C.F. (2009) Needed: A Global response to the Global Economic and Financial Crisis, International Institute of Economic Committee on Foreign Affairs, 12/3/09.
2. The gradual process of crisis took place in the world in the different countries with the varieties of financial instability Table 1 shows some of the exposition.
3. See Kumar & Raj and Pankaj Vashisht (2009), Global Economic Crisis : the India Pepective 8th India Koria Economic Dialogue New Delhi 2005-2009, ICRIER
4. See Prakash Anupam And Rajan Rajib (2012): Benchmarking India Rwgulatory Practices to the G 20 Financial Reforms Agenda, RBI, Department of economic And Policy Research, Bombay.
5. For detail see Report of the Commttee on Financial Inclusion, 2008, p.1.
6. Bhole, L.M., "Proposals for Financial Sector Reforms in India : An Appraisal," Vikalpa July-September, 1992.
7. Rangarajan, C, inancial Liberalization and Reforms," Discount and Finance, January 30 1992
8. Jana, Madan Mohan (2011) Corporate Financial Inclusion Plan in India : An Inclusive Growth Approach - An Empirical Study, the managemetn Account, October, P. 897
9. Agarwal, B.P. (1981), *Commercial Banking in India*, Classical Publishing Company, New Delhi.
10. Bansal, C.I., (1993). *Management of Commercial Banks in India : Financial Markets and Institutions*, Hiranand Publishing, New Delhi.
11. Chandrasekhar, M and Sonar, R. (2008). "Impact of Information Technology on Efficiency and Total Factor Productivity of Indian Banks," South Asian Journal of Management, Vol. 15, No. 3, pp.74-91.
12. Chu, L. F. (2003), "More Information Technology Investments, More Performance in Banking" Working Paper, Department of Finance, National Formosa University, Taiwan.
13. Cook, D. S. (1997). "Strucutural Change in the U. S. Commercial Banking Industry; The Role of Information Technology", Working Paper, ESA/OPA pp.97-106.
14. Kamadkodi N (2007). "Customer Preference on –Banking Services - Understandin through a sample Survey of Customers of Present day Banks in India" Cotributions, Vol. 4, pp. 30-43.
15. Dasgupta (2009), Two Approaches to Financial Inclusion, *Economic and Political Weekly*, Volume XLIV, Nos.26 and 27, p.41.
16. Chakkrabarty, K. C. 2011, Post Crisis" The New Normal" RBI Banque de France Seminar, Paris, November 8.
17. G20, 2011, Cannes Summit Final Declaration, November 4
18. Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2009 a *Strengthening he Resilience of the Banking Sector*, December (Basel)
19. Financial Stability Board, 2011a. *Overview of Proress in the Implementation to the G 20 Recommendation for Strengthening Financial Stability*. Report the Financial Stability Board to G20 Leaders, Nov. 4